

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

REPORT ON ACCELERATING CHANGE ACTIVITIES

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

**Funded by
the European Union**

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

**UK Research
and Innovation**

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
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This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

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PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Key deliverable information

Project acronym **PLANET4B**

Project title	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
Starting date	01 st November 2022
Duration	36 months
Website	https://planet4b.eu/
Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

Deliverable number **D5.7**

Deliverable title	Report on accelerating change activities
Task leader	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (UNEP-WCMC)
Corresponding author	Genevieve Beaufoy
Dissemination level	Public
Status	Final

Deliverable description

The report includes results of disseminating deliverables by participating in national and international scientific conferences, international and EU policy and business events, and channelling outcomes into communities, businesses and policies to accelerate change including gender, biodiversity and climate (CBD, IPBES, IPCC) processes and business and finance processes.

Version	Status	Date	Authors/Reviewers
0.1	Draft	20/09/2025	Author: Genevieve Beaufoy (UNEP-WCMC)
0.2	Draft	10/10/2025	Reviewers: Agnes Zolyomi (MLU); Lindy Binder (CU)
0.3	Draft	13/10/2025	Author: Genevieve Beaufoy (UNEP-WCMC)
0.4	Draft	14/10/2025	Reviewers: Agnes Zolyomi (MLU); Lindy Binder (CU)
0.5	Draft	15/10/2025	Author: Genevieve Beaufoy (UNEP-WCMC)
1.0	Final	23/10/2025	Reviewer: Torsten Wähler (MLU)

Recommended citation

Beaufoy, G. (2025). Report on accelerating change activities. Report No D5.7 of the Horizon Europe Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17243367

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Acknowledgements

The PLANET4B team would like to thank event hosts and participants, and colleagues working on related research initiatives and Horizon Europe projects, for their time and willingness to platform and engage with PLANET4B, share information, experiences, opinions, and collaborate to maximise project outcomes.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
ANZEE	The Australia New Zealand Society for Ecological Economics
CAC	The Climate Academy
CARN	Collaborative Action Research Network
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
CU	Coventry University
DC	Dadima's CIC.
EASST	European Association for the Study of Science and Technology
ECPR	European Consortium of Political Research
ESEE	European Society for Ecological Economics
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
EU	European Union
EURESFO	European Urban Resilience Forum
EYES	Empowering Youth through Environmental Storytelling project
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GD	GoodIssue nonprofit Ltd.
HBC	Human Behaviour Change for Life
IAPS	International Association People-Environment Studies
IASC	International Association for the Study of the Commons
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
ISDRS	International Sustainable Development Research Society
ISEE	International Society for Ecological Economics
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLU	Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg
NBS EduWORLD	Nature-Based Solutions Education Network
NERC	Nature Positive Workshop
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OOF	Oslo og Omland Friluftsråd – Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation

PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
RGS-IBG	Royal Geography Society – the Institute of British Geographers
RU	Radboud University
SIEF	International Society for Ethnology and Folklore
STS	Science and Technology Studies
TEHRA	The Environment and Human Rights Academy
UNEP-WCMC	UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa
4S	Society for Social Studies of Science

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Executive summary

- Throughout the three-year project life cycle, PLANET4B partners hosted and participated in 63 events in 20 countries, while conducting communication and collaboration activities to promote the project, disseminate outputs, and engage stakeholders.
- This report documents partner participation in conferences, lecture and seminar series, webinars, forums, and civic and professional events.

1 Introduction

Disseminating the insights, outcomes and lessons learnt in PLANET4B into societal, business, policy and research communities and processes is a key aim of the project, as outlined in Work Package 5 “Capacity building, cooperation, communication and upscaling to accelerate change”. This is crucial for engaging relevant stakeholders and ensuring impact during and beyond the project life cycle. Alongside the communication and dissemination activities (T5.1, T5.2) and cooperation with other initiatives and projects to foster synergies (T5.3), Task 5.4 "Channelling outcomes to accelerate change" contributes to this aim by participating in and hosting events and communication and collaboration activities.

This report documents the activities undertaken to accelerate change, in which consortium partners disseminated project insights, outcomes and deliverables by participating in national and international scientific conferences, and international and EU policy and business events. T5.4 also involved channelling outcomes into communities, business and policy processes, to accelerate change in relevant areas such as biodiversity, gender, finance and agriculture. A range of methods, platforms, and tools were utilised to disseminate project outcomes, including presentations at conferences, hosting and/or participating in workshops, conducting consultations, contributing to civic and professional events, seminars, webinars, social media posts, website updates and newsletters.

2 Methodological approach

2.1 Event scoping and coordination

Consortium partners utilised their existing networks and affiliations, known databases and platforms to identify events where PLANET4B deliverables and outcomes could be disseminated. In addition, UNEP-WCMC conducted event scoping and mapping, developing an Excel database of upcoming events of relevance identified on platforms such as LinkedIn, EU Agenda, Conal Conference Alerts, and Conferences in Europe. Relevant events and important information such as location, date, cost and thematic focus was gathered and shared among the consortium via email, within meetings between task leads, project coordinators and partners, on section 5 ‘Events’ on the project Miro board, and within the monthly newsletter. Partners were reminded to record event-related dissemination activities during Work Package lead meetings, communications meetings, and consortium meetings. Partners coordinated to determine who best to participate, with consideration for partners’ expertise in the

subject matter, those responsible for relevant tasks and activities within the project, and logistical considerations such as geographical location.

Events were prioritised based upon their relevance to the thematic research areas of PLANET4B (e.g. transformative change), and those related to the subject-matter of at least one of the eleven case studies (e.g. a conference on urban agriculture). Additionally, events that provided the best opportunity for PLANET4B messages to be heard by the target audiences in policy, business, and civil society were prioritised.

2.2 Data collection

Partners recorded their attendance and participation in events via the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation database developed by Good Issue (GI). UNEP-WCMC conducted follow-ups with partners and coordinated with Task leads and project coordinators to ensure databases were up to date. The specific information relating to event participation was extracted and recorded in this report.

3 Results

The following tables (1, 2, 3) document events (in-person and online) hosted, chaired and/or participated in by the PLANET4B consortium partners, where insights, outcomes and/or deliverables were shared. The information is arranged within three tables, corresponding to the three years of the project and includes conferences, webinars, lecture series and seminars, civic and professional events and key meetings of relevance. Table 4 lists a broader range of dissemination activities with Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) relevant to accelerating change activities. A more detailed account of digital media communication and dissemination activities can be found in deliverable 5.3 ‘Final communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategy’, while deliverable 5.6 ‘Updated synergies strategy’ documents activities in collaboration with other projects.

Table 1. Project Year 1 (2023).

Event	Date	Location	Partner participation
Seminar ‘The ecological challenge: A permanent transition?’	26 January	Bologna, Italy	UNIFI presented.
1st EU Cluster Event ‘Transformative Change for Biodiversity’	17 March	Brussels, Belgium	MLU presented. PLANET4B go on to co-lead the ‘Values, Norms and Justice’ working group of the cluster.
Conference ‘The new priority? Public opinion, politics, and policies in the age of climate change’	12 May	Milan, Italy	UNIFI participated.
Edible Cities Network Conference ‘Advancing the Edible City’	15–17 May	Barcelona, Spain	FUG and IFZ presented a poster on case study ‘City food for biodiversity and inclusion’.

Transformation durch Kooperation IV (Transformation through Cooperation IV)	2 June	Graz, Austria	FUG and IFZ presented a poster on case study 'City food for biodiversity and inclusion'.
SIEF2023: 16th Congress Living Uncertainty conference	7–10 June	Brno, Czech Republic	ESSRG presented a research poster 'Forming human-nature relations in education: from instrumental to relational values'.
Bilateral meetings with Horizon Europe project BioTraCes	23 June (regular bimonthly catchups)	Online	Co-convening panel 'Transformative interventions for strengthening biodiversity commons'.
IASC Conference	19–24 June	Nairobi, Kenya	MLU and CU co-chaired two panels, 'Transformative interventions for strengthening biodiversity commons' and 'SDGs and the commons'.
Meeting of Working Group on Values, Norms and Justice from Horizon Europe Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	29 June	Online	UNEP-WCMC presented.
Breaking the Bias: Inspire Diversity in R&I Summer School	4–7 July	Athens, Greece	IFZ gave a keynote speech 'Unravelling Gender Bias in Research and Innovation' and moderated 'Stream 3 on Climate, Biodiversity, and Mobility' for young researchers at the summer school. ESSRG presented a research poster.
Transformations Community Conference 'Transformative partnerships for a better world'	11–19 July	Prague, Czech Republic	CG organised the event, FiBL presented.
ISDRS Conference 'Half-way through Agenda 2030: Assessing the 5Ps of SDGs (people, planet, prosperity, peace and partnership)'	11–13 July	Bandar Baru Bangi, Malaysia; Online	CU presented.
The Alternet Summer School 'Biodiversity and Society: science, policy and transformative change'	30 August – 9 September	Peyresq, France	ESSRG presented.
Conference of the European Consortium of Political Research (ECPR)	4–8 September	Prague, Czech Republic	RU organised the panel 'Advancing the Research Frontier on New Supply Chain Regulations: Connecting

			Processes from the Demand-Side and Supply-Side: Part 1'.
XIV Conference on Sociology of the Environment	9 September	Syracuse, Italy	UNIFI presented 'Towards transformative change through biodiversity prioritisation in governance: insights from the case of Tuscany's fashion system'.
Center for Global Cooperation Research Global Green Visions Workshop	11–12 September	Duisburg, Germany	RU presented.
Radbound Conference on Earth System Governance 'Bridging Sciences and Societies for Sustainability Transformations'	22–24 October	Nijmegen, Netherlands	MLU and CU organised a panel 'Transformative interventions to strengthen biodiversity prioritization'; IFZ presented 'Using an intersectional lens in co-developing interventions to strengthen the 'BioDiverse Edible City' concept in Graz, Austria'; UNIFI presented 'Understanding interventions for pro-biodiversity behaviour in a sectoral context: An example of the Tuscan textile, apparel, and fashion industries'.
Hungarian Science Festival	15 November	Budapest, Hungary	ESSRG presented 'Biodiversity assessment = diversity of assessment?'

Table 2. Project Year 2 (2024).

Event	Date	Location	Partner participation
TransformerERs COST Action Working Group meeting	4 March	Online	MLU presented.
Shared Green Deal webinar 'Diversity of values for countering biodiversity loss'	14 March	Online	MLU presented.
European Commission's Policy Forum 2024 – Education for Climate	17 April	Brussels, Belgium	CAC presented key PLANET4B concepts.
7th International Conference on Gender Research	25–26 April	Barcelona, Spain	IFZ presented 'Can Participatory Action Research Deepen the Understanding of Intersectionality in the Field of Biodiversity Research?'
STS Conference 'Critical issues in Science,	6–8 May	Graz, Austria	IFZ presented.

Technology and Society Studies'			
Symposium 'Continuing education in the field of tension of digital and sustainable transformation' (Vienna Chamber of Labour & Vienna Employee Promotion Fund (waff))	15 May	Vienna, Austria	IFZ presented.
VII AGROMIG International Seminar – Migrations, agrifood and rural change	23–24 May	Arcavacata, Italy	FiBL presented 'Linking agriculture, biodiversity conservation, and labour migration in the European Union'.
Meeting of Working Group on Values, Norms and Justice from Horizon Europe Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	7 June	Online	UNEP-WCMC co-chaired.
Plymouth University 'Developing Creative Research Practices'	13 June	Plymouth, UK	CU presented.
ISDRS Conference	10–14 June	Kathmandu, Nepal; Online	CU co-chaired session 'Theoretical approaches / public participation and the role of stakeholders'.
ESEE-Degrowth International Conference	19 June	Barcelona, Spain	ESSRG presented their case study 'Environmental awareness raising in education'.
Caring for Creation Summer School	4 July	Esztergom, Hungary	ESSRG presented.
IAPS annual conference	2–5 July	Barcelona, Spain	ESSRG presented their case study 'Environmental awareness raising in education'.
EASST-4S joint meeting of the European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST) and the Society for Social Studies of Science (4S)	16–19 July	Amsterdam, Netherlands	IFZ presented 'Feminist STS in the making: Experiences from translating intersectionality into health technology, artificial intelligence and biodiversity research'.
Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) Nature Positive Workshop	9 September	London, UK	UNEP-WCMC participated in sessions with industry experts, business

			leaders and policymakers, and shared insights from PLANET4B.
Transformative change seminars 1st webinar 'Conceptual frameworks on transformative change and stakeholder engagement'	12 September	Online	NINA and MLU presented on D1.7 and the RSM.
University of Paraíba seminar 'Topics in Environmental Governance: Big tech and Biodiversity Conservation'	13 September	Paraíba, Brazil	RU presented.
Meeting of Working Group on Values, Norms and Justice from Horizon Europe Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster	4 October	Online	UNEP-WCMC participated.
ANZEE Biennial Conference	4–7 October	North Stadbroke Island, Australia; Online	ESSRG presented keynote lecture 'The role of education in transformative change and the potential contribution of ecological economics'.
Norsk Friluftsliv Conference 'Research in Outdoor Life'	28 November	Oslo, Norway	NINA, OOF presented 'Inclusion of children with disabilities in outdoor life: the perspectives of outdoor organizations'.
Conference: Contemporary Challenges: 'Citizen Science' in the Humanities and Social Sciences, Public Science, Interdisciplinarity, the Boundaries of Sciences	2–3 December	Pécs, Hungary	ESSRG conducted three sessions: 'Enhancing environmental values through experiential learning methods – a participatory study in school gardens'; Reflections on Citizen Social Science as an Emerging Participatory Research Practice: Some Lessons from the 'YouCount – Youth Citizen Science' project', and 'Moving away from a citizen science experiment: Agrobiodiversity through participatory research'.

Table 3. Project Year 3 (2025).

Event	Date	Location	Partner participation
Sustainable Urban Futures seminar by GreenSmart, NMBU Sustainability Arena	15 January	Ås, Norway	NINA co-presented panel 'Just Cities for All'.
Nature Action Dialogues	25–26 March	Cambridge, UK	UNEP-WCMC co-chaired session 'Every job is a nature job: Integrating nature across key business functions'.
Transgress Conference by EAT+CHANGE	10–11 April	Graz, Austria	IFZ presented 'Gaia Gartenberg: Learning about perspectives on diversity and biodiversity in a garden for and by women*'.
Amplifying community voices workshops	April	Kigali, Rwanda	CU held a series of workshop with local communities about transformative change and biodiversity.
1st European Symposium 'Fostering Cultivated Biodiversity through Local Food Policies'	29–30 April	Granollers, Spain	IFZ presented a poster.
STS conference 'Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies'	5–7 May	Graz, Austria	IFZ co-chaired a session: 'Co-creative approaches (learning spaces) for (agro-)biodiversity positive and socially' just transformative changes', presenting decision-making tools tested within PLANET4B.
'Gender in Focus' Lecture Series	13 May	Jena, Germany; Online	IFZ presented 'Generating 'robust knowledge' through gender- and diversity-sensitive research – from successful individual examples to a lived organizational strategy'.
Alternet Conference	13–16 May	Aveiro, Portugal	ESSRG chaired a session on PLANET4B transformative change stories; CU presented keynote and presentation of participatory film with DC; IFZ presented.
Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster workshop and conference 'Mainstreaming Biodiversity in Policy Making'	4–5 June	Brussels, Belgium	CU contributed.

IASC Conference 'Regenerating the Commons: Addressing Pressing Concerns Through Learning about the Past and Innovating into the Future'	16–20 June	Amherst, USA; Online	MLU and CU co-chaired panel 'Societal transformations and biodiversity: Understanding the interplay of institutional, interpersonal and intrapersonal change'; RU presented a session 'Intersectional Environmental in Dutch-Brazilian Beef and Soy Supply Chains: Challenges for the EUDR'
EURESFO NBS EduWORLD 'Collaborate, Educate, Transform: Building the Future of Nature-based Solutions in Cities'	26 June	Rotterdam, Netherlands	CU presented learning materials.
ISEE-Degrowth Conference 'Building socially just postgrowth futures – linking theory and action'	24–27 June	Oslo, Norway	ESSRG presented and chaired a session; UNIPI contributed.
Halle Day of Sociology at Martin Luther University of Halle-Wittenberg	4 July	Halle, Germany	MLU keynote presentation on 'Response-Able Social-Environmental Transformations: Why and How?'
ISDRS conference	8–12 July	Budapest, Hungary	CU chaired.
RGS-IBG Conference 'Geographies of Creativity'	26–29 August	Birmingham, UK	CU presented two papers.
Let's Liberate Diversity Forum	4–6 September	Luxembourg	FUG presented poster.
HBC Fest – a Festival for Changemakers	5–7 September	Lincolnshire, UK	CU presented and hosted biodiversity games.
PLANET4B Tales of Transformation: Turning the Tide for Biodiversity and People	11 September	Brussels, Belgium; Online	UNEP-WCMC chaired (PLANET4B final event), all partners presented.
Barrier-Free Conference 'How can we ensure barrier-free leisure time for all children and people?'	24 September	Oslo, Norway	OOF presented.
Symposium 'Konsum Nedenken' (Rethinking consumption)	26 September	Vienna, Austria	IFZ presented.

Transformative Change Seminars webinar #4 'Tools for Transformative Change for Biodiversity'	29 September	Online	MLU presented 'Empowering biodiversity action through PLANET4B's PATHBREAK and Biodiversity engagement platform'.
Capitals Coalition A-Track event	6 October	Online	CU presented on business behaviour change methods.
NINA and OOF seminar in collaboration with local and regional authorities (KS og Akershus fylkeskommune) and the disability interest organisation Unge funksjonshemmede (young disabled)	9 October	Oslo, Norway	NINA and OOF disseminated information on case study 'Enabling intersectional nature recreation and biodiversity stewardship for urban resilience'.
GoDigiBios webinar 'New innovative solutions for transforming urban areas via biodiversity boost'	15 October	Online	CU and MLU presented.
EYES Workshop for Educators on climate education, storytelling, systems and alternative economic thinking, and emotional resilience	14–16 October	Brussels, Belgium	TEHRA (previously CAC) delivered a PLANET4B lesson and presented materials to 15 European educators (secondary school education).
University of Mons conference 'How to prepare yourself and young people for the socio-ecological transition?'	16 October	Mons, Belgium	TEHRA (previously CAC) co-hosting and presenting PLANET4B materials.

Table 4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) relevant to accelerating change activities.*
Source: PLANET4B updated CDE (showing KPI statuses as of October 2025).

Tools	KPI	Target	Results (October 2025)
Website	No. of visitors	5.000	6000–6500 (estimated)
Newsletter	No. of subscribers	200	200
Social media	No. of followers	1.000	1050
	No. of posts	700	705
Videos, illustrations and artwork	No. of videos produced	10	25
	No. of target groups reached	500	1300 views of videos (plus additional outreach through dissemination)
Infographics	No. of infographics	5	5
	No. of target groups reached	500	n.a.
Press release	No. of press releases sent	5	4 on project level (plus 9 released by PPs)
Non-scientific articles (e.g. The Conversation), radio and TV interviews	No. of articles	30	48 on the external channels plus 40 on the website
	No. of radio interviews	5	4 (2 FIBL podcasts, 2 ESSRG)
	No. of TV interviews, spots	2	n.a.
	No. of people reached	100 000	71 223
Scientific publications	No. of publications	5	7
Workshops for enabling players and stakeholders	No. of workshops organised	64	63
	No. of participants	200	412**
Consultations	No. of consultations	10	29
Joint actions with other EU projects (e.g. joint event, joint communication)	No. of actions	10	26
Presentations at scientific conferences and events	No. of presentations	5	72
Public deliverables	No. of deliverables	28	29
Deliverable briefs (a creative, short version of the main messages)	No. of briefs	25	20
Online training	No. of online trainings	1	4 (exploitation and dissemination is planned after M36)
	No. of target group participants	300	
	No. of education	100	

	institutes/youth groups reached		
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* Total number of target audience reached (documented) from all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

** As some of the workshops and events overlapped with other categories, such as conferences and events, the actual number of participants is substantially greater, but at least 412 have been reported in the workshops category.

3.5 Key findings

Throughout the life cycle of the project, the PLANET4B consortium participated in 63 events spanning 20 countries. Project partners participated in local, national, regional and international events. The nature of participation included the coordination of panels, conducting presentations and keynote speeches, interactive activities and the dissemination of project materials and outputs. The majority of events attended by partners were interdisciplinary, with thematic areas comprising education, transformative change for biodiversity, gender, ecological economics, urban sustainability, resilience and inclusion, participatory and creative research, and intersectionality. Project partners also engaged with civic, policy and business communities by hosting and attending events with stakeholders local to case studies, business actors and within policy forums, for example.

3.6 Limitations

Only events within the project life cycle could be attended, with some key conferences of relevance taking place outside of the project window. In addition, with a large consortium such as the PLANET4B, it can be challenging to record and gather in-depth information about event participation. However, the development of partnerships and collaborative opportunities provided by participating in events has created opportunities for further dissemination of PLANET4B messages and lessons learnt for future projects.

4 Conclusion and outlook

The PLANET4B consortium found having a dedicated budget for participating in events a very valuable aspect of Horizon Europe research projects, as it enables and encourages the cross-fertilisation of knowledge. Attending events gave project partners the opportunity to strengthen partnerships and build new relationships, increasing the chance of impact and collaboration beyond the life cycle of the project. This was helped by a strong and growing community and practice of research working on similar topics, such as the Horizon Europe cluster on Transformative Change for Biodiversity.

Participating in events while undertaking concurrent tasks within the project not only ensured the broad dissemination of PLANET4B insights, outcomes, and deliverables, but also allowed for an iterative process of continued learning and inspiration for the delivery of upcoming tasks, by exposure to and engagement with research, policy, business and civic communities. Project partners will also be participating in future events, ensuring that this method of accelerating change can be impactful beyond the duration of the project. IFZ will be presenting at CARN conference 'Digitalization, social

justice and transforming societies' on 13–15 November; TEHRA (previously CAC) will be presenting PLANET4B materials at the School for Advanced Studies in Social Sciences on 6 November in Paris; PLANET4B partners will be contributing to the upcoming Transformative Change Cluster Projects event with Horizon Europe projects DAISY, BAMBOO, BIONEXT, BioTraCes, TRANSPATH, TC4BE and CirCHive on 4–5 June 2026.

Statement on data availability

Data used to generate this report is available to the consortium on the CU PLANET4B SharePoint, within the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation database.

Statement on ethics

The content in this D5.7 Report on Accelerating Change Activities has been developed based on data provided by project partners, there were no ethical considerations or potential conflicts of interest.